

PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND MASS SPORTS

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ABSTRACT

The article is about the problems and solutions of Science Education in the field of physical education and sports, the study of professional educational benchmarks in physical education and sports activity of athletes, the close connection of sports federations with sports organizations in professional sports education, the formation of various sports education studies between problem situations and sports organizations of education.

As noted in the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 414 of November 2022, it is envisaged to obtain high results by training qualified personnel in the field of Physical Education and sports, adapting the educational process to international standards and digitizing the management system, further improving the pedagogical and scientific potential and radically improving the quality of research

Formation of educational programs according to the program of a foreign higher educational institution with a high international rating, to ensure the academic exchange of students in cooperation with the world's leading higher educational institutions and to create broad conditions for Education, Accreditation of Bachelor's degrees and master's specialties, Organization of the educational process on the basis of a credit-modular system in order to constantly improve sports skills in students and to express their person on the basis of, graduates 'pre-graduation practice consists in organizing them by involving them in the process of training and training sessions of national teams abroad, as well as international competitions, based on the level of application of the students' knowledge, qualifications and skills in practice, providing talented graduates with certificates determining the qualification category of a sports referee and a second-class trainer.

The development of sports, the wide resolution of a healthy lifestyle in our society, the popularization of physical education and sports among the population, especially among

young people, have been marked as a sign of the important directions of the policy of our state since the first days of independence.

Over the years, large-scale work has been carried out on this subject and tremendous results have been achieved. Over the past five years, 1 trillion 230 billion soums have been allocated for the development of Physical Culture and sports, as well as strengthening its material and technical base, and funds from the National Olympic Committee of Uzbekistan have also been spent.

Today, in order to further expand the mass involvement of children in sports, about 114, 8 thousand sports sections are operating in 1,700 children's sports facilities, which means 30 percent more than the 2020 indicators.

More than 3, 6 million residents are involved in sports sections and groups organized in gyms and sports clubs of all Umut education schools, children's and youth sports schools, academic lyceums and professional colleges in the Republic. More than 2, 1 million of them are students and young people of secondary schools, professional colleges and academic lyceums.

Today, 10 thousand 75 teachers and coaches operate in sports facilities in the Republic, of which 4 thousand 667 are of Higher Education (43, 4 percent, 5 thousand 599 are of secondary special education (56, 6 percent).

Today our country is literally becoming a sports country. A healthy lifestyle among young people is widely decided and the popularity of sports is ensured. Athletes of Uzbekistan have won high victories in prestigious World competitions and show the sports potential of our country to the whole world. The results achieved by our athletes at the 2016 Olympic and Paralympic Games in Brazil and 2021 in Japan alone made our country known to the world sports community as a dynamically developing country. We are rightfully proud of this.

But it is also necessary to say that in recognition of the achieved results, achievements, there are serious shortcomings and problems in improving the system of organization and management of the physical education and sports sphere, strengthening the material and technical base of the industry, broad involvement of youth in sports in the regions, creating sufficient conditions for them, training qualified personnel in For example, today, 67.6% of 9,698 secondary schools in the system of the Ministry of Public Education have gyms, while 32.4% do not have gyms. In total, 25 thousand 603 teachers of physical education work in schools. 17 thousand 735 of them (69.2 percent) have higher education, 7 thousand 868 (30.8 percent) have secondary special education.

The number of teachers with secondary special education in the discipline of physical education is the majority in Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya, Samarkand, Tashkent, Khorezm regions. The educational and methodological manual for teachers in the discipline of physical education was created in 2003, so far this manual has not been reprinted. There are 225 sports schools on the territory of the Republic, of which 53 are specialized sports schools for sports. In total, there are 318,693 people in these schools, of which 97,000 girls are regularly engaged in children's Sports, which means only 7.1% of total schoolchildren.

Also, since skilled athletes face the problem of employment of graduate-athletes or material support of the family after graduating from professional colleges, especially Olympic Reserve colleges, cases of dropping out of a big sport or leaving for foreign countries at a time

when only high results are shown, remain one of the most pressing problems. There are defects in maintaining at the required level of sports facilities, the effective use of which has been entrusted in Awalgi years.

According to this decree, the Ministry of sports development of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established and all sports facilities in the structure of the Ministry of public education of the Republic of Uzbekistan were transferred to these, 225 sports schools, 37 sports boarding schools, the Ministry of sports development. The main goal is to strengthen the Olympic movement through the development of children's sports in Uzbekistan, further expand the ranks of physical education and sports practitioners, improve the physical fitness and health of children, ensure effective participation of Uzbek sportsmen in Asia and the Olympic Games, various prestigious international competitions.

At the same time, the main tasks and directions of the committee - creating conditions for children to engage in sports, especially improving these activities in rural areas, creating skills in a healthy lifestyle between them, increasing the level of experience and knowledge in this regard, educating them in a patriotic spirit, radically improving the quality of the physical education and educational process, creating a holistic system of effective training of highly qualified athletes, further strengthening, important tasks such as providing modern sports equipment and equipment for training and competitions have been identified.

In turn, it should be noted that one of the main tasks facing the Ministry of sports development is the development, improvement and implementation of laws, regulatory and legal acts in the field of sports based on the demand of the time.

"On measures for the further development of Physical Education and mass sports", "on additional measures for the development of annual and equestrian sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan", "on the preparation of athletes of Uzbekistan for the XXXIII Summer Olympic and XVII Paralympic Games to be held in Paris (France) in 2024 for a short time, Decisions were developed and signed by the president" on the broad involvement of athletes of Uzbekistan in public and sports activities and the promotion of athletes and their trainers who have achieved high results in prestigious international sports competitions". Suggestions and considerations. At present, amendments and additions to the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on Physical Culture and sports", the establishment of sports clubs, the creation of a system for assessing activities in the field of sports, recognition of sports and sports networks, their inclusion in the Register of sports and the regulation on the procedure for maintaining this register, the regulation on the procedure, The Republic of Uzbekistan is working on proposals for the preparation of relevant documents and improvement of current documents on approval of the regulation on uniform sports classification. The mentioned documents will undoubtedly serve as a kind of foundation for the development of the sports sphere in our country. The decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures for the further development of Physical Culture and mass sports" and the "program for the further development of Physical Culture and mass sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan" in accordance with this decision will serve to positively solve the issues awaiting the solution.

In order to ensure the implementation of the decision of the head of state on the preparation of athletes of Uzbekistan for the XXXIII Summer Olympic and XVII Paralympic Games in Paris (France) in 2024, a number of works are being carried out together with the

National Olympic Committee of Uzbekistan, sports organizations to qualify talented athletes and form national teams,

It provides an opportunity for them to make a worthy contribution to the preparation of the reserve of athletes who successfully participate in prestigious international competitions.

In the last period, the number and weight of achievements of our athletes at the Asian and World Championships has grown significantly. In particular, during the seven months of this year, representatives of our country have adequately defended the honor of our motherland in more than 120 prestigious competitions held abroad. In total, Uzbek athletes were promoted to the podium 773 times: 292 gold medals, 221 silver medals, 261 bronze medals were included in the QO. The fact that our athletes won gold medals in nine of the ten weight categories at the Asian Boxing Championships in Tashkent in May raised the mood of our people, donated wonderful joyful moments.

By a healthy generation, we mean, first of all, a healthy generation, only physically strong, at the same time healthy in spirit, thought, faith-faith as a whole, educated, high in spirituality, brave and courageous, patriotic generation. Only a healthy nation, a healthy generation can build this state. Because the dream of a healthy generation is a sacred aspiration that is passed on to us from our ancestors, permeated with our blood. If we look at the way of life, thinking of our ancestors, we will see that they paid too much attention to procreation, the purity of the seven pugs, the health of the offspring. But raising a healthy generation is not an easy task. It requires serious attention and continuous work from every person, every family, society as a whole. For the motherland, for its children and for future generations, everyone should be able to do well-deserved deeds. According to the noble imagination and understanding of our noble people, every person should come into the world and do three good deeds. The first is to raise and raise a healthy and intelligent child. The second is to build a castle for his family, children. The third is to plant a tree with good intentions, thinking about the future. Because in these human aspirations, the dreams of the harmonious generation of our nation are reflected. In the meaning of all the dreams and life of Uzbekistan, we see goals related to the future of their children, happiness.

Our great-grandfather Amir Temur said, "The Soldiers of the mighty el will be mighty, and the soldiers of the mighty El will be strong". Continuing this idea, our first president I.Karimov said that "the children of a healthy country will be powerful, the children of a mighty land will be healthy." If the child is healthy, reasonable, faith-believing, he will only bring thanks to his parents, bring a breath to people, will never remain from the point of view of el-yurt. The upbringing of a healthy generation requires serious attention and work from every person, every family, society as a whole. It is natural for common sense to come out of people with a healthy soul and a healthy body. Wide-minded, sharp-witted and talented people are called geniuses. Works, discoveries, noble works created by geniuses, that is, perfect people, will belong to all of humanity, and they will be able to influence world development with their mature work in their field.

One of the instructive aspects of our ancestors, our momos, for us is that they were extremely hardworking, hardworking. Our ancestors considered the secret of a comfortable and full life to be in honest labor. They also encouraged their children to work, to live in exchange for forehead skin. When a person lives in this world, he strives to achieve

something, to find something. Someone is looking for happiness, and someone is the throne. Someone is looking for wealth, someone else is fame. Of course, this is a way of struggle for survival, which everyone wants: however, people want to find something in the course of their actions, and also face losses. Peace and quiet in fasting largely depends on the relationship of their parents. When a parent is a cow, this in itself serves as an example for children, young people who have grown up in a close family also live a sweet life like their father. The family is the basis of society. When the family is healthy, the nation is also healthy.

The foundation is also laid in the family for the health, physical and mental perfection of the next generation. According to the custom of our people, each person must carry out three good deeds throughout his life, that is, the duty to raise 226 healthy and harmonious children, build a shelter for his family and plant seedlings with good intentions is absorbed in our blood. Every parent dreams that his child will grow up in Perfection, will adequately fulfill his duty to his homeland. And the first stage of spiritual perfection begins with a focus on Physical Culture and sports at a higher level. Our First President I.Karimov In the following words of, this can be understood even more deeply: "through sports, the child's worldview changes. A child who walked the street yesterday, not knowing what to do, will also look at his parents with a different eye if he is busy with work and sports activities by learning a craft. In the family, Kindness, Harmony increases. Boys in particular pass a school of bravery on sports grounds." It is known to everyone today that in order to educate and educate the perfect generation, first of all, it is necessary to form in them a love of sports, and in the pursuit of these noble goals, our president creates all opportunities.

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